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Research Data Management for Master student Research Projects

Do you supervise Master students? This document explains how you can advise your Master students to work safely with research data in thesis and internship projects. It is written by the [EUR Research Data Stewards](#) and is intended for EUR researchers supervising Master students.

What data does your student work with?

Pay attention to what type of data is collected by students.

Personal Data

If a master thesis project involves collecting data from/about human participants, it is very likely that your students are working with [personal data](#). Personal data should always be handled with care. Before collecting personal data, your students should give their participants information about the thesis project and processing of their personal data and ask for consent to use this information.

Some personal data are [more sensitive](#) than others. If data involves information about one's racial or ethnic origin, political views, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, health, sex life or sexual orientation or if it constitutes genetic data or biometric data, it qualifies as a [special category](#) of personal data (see this [glossary](#) for details). Your students should treat this data with extra care and use it only to the extent necessary for their project after having taken additional safeguards.

Students who collect personal data should be advised to use a safe storage solution and privacy-compliant tools (for example, MS Teams instead of Zoom, SURFdrive instead of Dropbox, etc.). The necessity for safe storage and additional security measures becomes paramount when special category of personal data or otherwise sensitive data is collected. Using personal data will also have implications for data sharing (if applicable, see section [Is my student required to preserve data for the long-term?](#)).

Non-personal Sensitive Data

Even when your student's research does not contain personal data, it may concern sensitive data such as company secrets or national security information. If so, we recommend using safe storage options. Please note that legal arrangements that you make with the data provider may dictate where the data should be stored. Please consult with the [Research Data Steward](#) and [Privacy Officer](#) at your faculty.

What do we consider anonymized data?

Students working with personal data must make sure that their thesis does not contain any personal data. They should consider appropriate measures to protect the privacy of their research participants. One way to do so is by anonymizing or pseudonymizing their research data. We talk about fully anonymized data when the **research participants cannot be identified** and the user of data cannot trace it back to them (for example, an anonymous online survey with a limited number of questions). If the researcher removes identifiable information from the collected data, but keeps the key file or original dataset, we talk about pseudonymized data. Students should make sure that their data is properly anonymized before making their thesis publicly available or before giving others access to their data.

More information: [Anonymization of Research Data](#).

What should students pay attention to when anonymizing their own data?

There is a common misconception that removing/deleting names and last names is sufficient to make data anonymous. If students would like to go through the [anonymization process](#), they should be aware that there are different techniques for [qualitative](#) and [quantitative](#) data (note that anonymization of qualitative data and audio data can be very difficult).

A couple of practical tips:

- Change Qualtrics setting to stop registering IP addresses and location coordinates ([Anonymize Responses section](#)) (note, that this is not a bullet proof solution as personal information might be also asked in the questionnaire).
- [Anonymization of qualitative data – a practical approach](#)

Where should students store their data during the master thesis project?

Data collected during the master thesis project (e.g., datasets, surveys, readings, notes, images) should be stored on EUR cloud storage. This is recommended over a local device and external drive, as it minimizes the risk of losing files and students can access them anywhere. As a default, they can use Microsoft OneDrive for free, tied to their EUR account (a [mini tutorial](#) to see how to use OneDrive). If the research project contains special category of personal data or sensitive data, you should consult your Privacy Officer and to use a safer solution. See this [Tooling page](#) for an overview. Most are available for researchers only, so can be accessed with the help of the supervisor. Regardless of the chosen storage solution, make sure that you and your students are aware of [EUR Cybersecurity guidelines](#) to work as safely as possible.

If you are interested in reusing the data collected by your students for your own research project or publication, you must reach out to your Privacy Officer before the data collection begins and make sure that the right legal framework is in place that would allow you to lawfully re-use the data for your own research.

How to share data with students?

For sharing data with students, the project-based tools are recommended: [EUR Yoda](#), [SURFdrive](#), [SURF Research Drive](#), or [EUR MS Teams / SharePoint](#). Note that it is important to restrict access to only the data that is needed for the student project (preferably anonymized data). In EUR Yoda, access is managed at project level, in that case it is best to create a specific project with a subset of data for student projects. In SURF Research Drive and MS Teams, there are possibilities to give specific access rights to individual files and folders. Remember that sharing your data with your students may not always be permissible. Consult your Privacy Officer to determine if sharing data with your students is allowed and if there are any additional measures required to make it possible.

What tools for data collection and processing should students use?

For collecting and processing the data, students should use EUR-supported software as listed in the [EUR software catalog](#). For surveys, EUR managed tools such as [Qualtrics](#) are recommended. In cases where additional software is needed, the supervisor should contact the faculty IT Demand Manager or the [IT Service Desk](#). For more information, see also [Tools for Data Collection, Processing and Analysis](#).

How should students organize their folders and name their files?

If you would like to give students tips about folder organization during the research project, you can consult the [Data Documentation](#) page. See also [Best practices for documenting and organizing research projects](#) for tips about file names and organization.

Is my student required to preserve data for the long-term?

Master thesis projects do not fall under the [EUR RDM policy](#), therefore data preservation or data sharing is not expected. However, the EUR RDM policy becomes applicable if a master thesis project turns into an academic publication. Then, students under guidance of their supervisor should deposit research data for long-term preservation for verification purposes (note that for research data involving human participants it is necessary to contact the privacy officer and apply for ethical approval *before* data collection – otherwise it cannot be used for academic publications). In cases where the thesis project is not intended for academic publication and the data contains personal or sensitive information, it is strongly urged to delete the data after the project. Such data should not be stored longer than necessary.

Do master students fill in Data Management Plans?

For projects that require ethics approval, a Data Management Plan is highly recommended (and mandatory at some schools). For those projects, Master students can complete a Data Management Plan under guidance of their supervisor.

Useful professional support staff contacts

Data Stewards: <https://my.eur.nl/en/rsp-employee/services/data-management-support>

Privacy Officers: <https://my.eur.nl/en/rsp-employee/services/data-protection-support-and-advice>

Useful templates

Data Management Plan: <https://www.eur.nl/en/research/research-services/research-data-management/data-management-plan>